

METHODS OF TEACHING YOUNG PEOPLE TO COMMUNICATION IN PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

In this article, it is recommended to read Psychological, pedagogical literature in teaching young people to communicate, to observe the activity of young people in the process of communication, to determine their thinking, and in this process to use psychological games, exercises, trainings, as well as to communicate according to adult data, age, gender, profession, the peculiarity of communication of the elderly, they need it is thought that it is important to apply more words to them that raise their hearts.

Introduction. Educating young people not only as energetic, but also spiritually rich, responding to the demand for a new era, thinking freely in the process of communication is one of the pressing problems of the present day. The law "on education" focuses on the primary emphasis on the content of the culture of communication, forming an independent thinking ability of the person's land. Therefore, the formation of the skills of free expression of independent thoughts and their critical thinking in the process of communication of adolescents and adults is one of the topical issues facing educators. [1]

After all, for the critical thinking of every person living in the XXI century, it is necessary to first teach communication. In order to teach students to communicate, it is important to recommend them to read Psychological, pedagogical literature, to observe the activity of young people in the

process of communication, to determine their thinking, and in this process to use psychological games, exercises, trainings.

One of our high spiritual needs is the need for communication. Our consciousness does not develop either, unless our need for communication is satisfied. Therefore, we must always meet our need for communication. [2] With whom we are satisfied with communication, in some cases we feel dissatisfied. Older people enter into formal and informal relationships. Formal relationships are on the job, service. Informal communication occurs at other times from work, at home (family), in the neighborhood, in the bosom.

In adult communication, a culture of communication is often carried out, that is, respect for each other, trust, understanding, etc. But at some times, communication disorders are also possible. Because adults at some times can be offended without understanding each other, saying

something unpleasant to the soul, as a result of which they can come up with disputes. If the culture of communication is well formed in people, then it is easy for them to understand each other. [3] The culture of communication can be formed from youth in the family, under the influence of the social environment, as a result of self-awareness, upbringing. The fact that we become an example, a lesson for adult youth comes from our communication with each other. From the "golden words" (greatest, circle, duck, you are so wonderful, today you are different, open up, like your clothes are very reconciled), we need to use more in our everyday life. Through the imitation of young people in adult communication, the art of treatment, culture are formed in them. Especially in the family we should pay attention to these situations. Because the transplant "does what the bird sees in the nest" is not accidental.

Adults also have a verbal, nonverbal and paralingvistic effect on each other. We can also influence each other through gestures, mimics, pauses when the time comes. With a word of mouth we can either rejoice, or offend. Therefore, it is always necessary for adults to be sincerely attached to each other and influence. [4]

Adult communication becomes specific at a certain age. For example, adults communicate depending on their data, age, gender, profession. Communication of the elderly is unique. They are just as demanding, capricious, demanding of attention as small children. It is necessary to treat the elderly with caution, because their hearts will be thin. It is necessary to apply to them more words that will raise their hearts.

This means that people of all ages, including adults, begin to communicate in

their own way. Communication is carried out in the specific case for each period.

In the formation of individual communication, it is necessary to conduct work taking into account his age, sex, profession, outlook. For example, we do not use words that we use in relation to adults to small children. Specific words are used to people entering each age period. In this word, the force of action is taken into account. Of great importance is the use of methods of communication, depending on the temperament characteristics of the individual. The role of communication in the formation of skills, knowledge, skills in a person can not be overestimated. Simple skills ("sit down properly, wash your hands, go where you are, say hello") are also absorbed by communication. [5]

In the formation of individual communication, the level of his upbringing plays an important role. For example, even if you use words that strongly affect a person, he or she may not accept, he or she may not follow your instructions. Because he must master the culture of treatment from an early age. In the formation of communication, the goal should be set correctly. Communication develops in the process of education, in different situations. For example, in the family, in the neighborhood, in the team, in the group. If adults in the family are in a rough relationship with each other, the child can also go to conflicts with those around them, imitating them.

We put before us the upbringing of a comprehensively developed, mature, perfect person (person). The president of our country always inspires the education of young people by thinking freely. [6] It means that communication is formed in connection with thinking on its own.

Research Methodology. About the importance of communication in the formation of a person, several psychologist scientists have already described their opinion. In particular, the Russian psychologist B.G. Ananov analyzed this issue in depth in his work "as a subject of human knowledge". He argues that the possession of various elements of knowledge is a guarantee of successful assimilation. Knowledge acquisition will also take effect through communication. If people do not share information with each other, if they do not share their experiences through communication, they will develop. G. Ananov brings grounded thoughts.

B.G. "Communication is social and individual," Ananov said. Therefore, speech is associated with self, pantomime in the performance of a communicative task, gestures arise as a form of communication.

Hence, the scientist gave an in-depth analysis of the concept of communication for such subjects as general, young and pedagogical psychology.

At present, interest in the problem of communication in our country and abroad is growing. In the conditions of a market economy, the communication that people do with each other is of great importance. Another of the outstanding psychologist scientists V.N. Myasnikov deeply sympathized with the issue of communication, studied it. If other scientists have studied the connection of communication with speech communication, V.N. Myasnikov studied communication as a process. That is, it analyzes the interaction of individuals with each other through communication, as an object of perception of each other. In his opinion: "a person can manifest dependent qualities in different relationships,"

Experienced psychologist A.A. And Bodalev realized that a person needs to know his place in the game, in reading, in communication, that is, in different spheres of activity. He pays great attention to this issue in his book "personality and society". He also points out that these problems are poorly studied. A. A. Bodalev believes that "when educating a person through communication, it is necessary to think first about how this affects him." [7]

Psychologists A. on the role of communication in Personality Development A. Lyublinskaya, D.B. Elkonin emphasize the formation of communication through play activities in the child. P. on the formation of the character, willpower qualities of a person by means of communication. E. Galperin, N.F. Dabra's, N.F. The taluzines conducted their own research.

Also, one of the Republic's psychologists M.G. Davletshin, E. Gaziev, N.P. Anikeeva, N. Safoev vs. enlightened the problem of communication from different sides. In particular, professor E. In the textbook "psychology of treatment" goziev tried to clarify from the theoretical side all aspects of communication. Professor M.G. Davletshin also expressed his thoughts on how communication is formed in people in the textbook "general psychology".

In the successful conduct of youth communication, the importance of the formed qualities, qualities of an individual is very great. In particular, the process of communication also goes well if positive qualities are well formed in a person (like politeness, modesty, humanism, correct vocabulary, conscience). Because in order for individuals to understand each other properly, they must be sincere in order for communication to succeed.

Sincerity is one of the most amazing qualities of a person, to be able to react intelligently to events, not to be given different influences. An important sign of sincerity is a kind expression and a smile on the face. Sincerity also depends on our mood, because if our mood is good, then sincerity will move. To show sincerity, one's soul must be clean, whitish. [8]The virtue of sincerity is especially important in the communication that the leader makes with his employees. If the leader is not in an intimate relationship with the employees, their mood may fall and labor productivity may decrease.

Some leaders are in a rough, insensitive relationship with the subordinates and act according to the autocratic style in the tone of the command.

The famous American speaker, psychologist Dale Carnegie, shows in his book that a leader has always been a coward, not in an intimate relationship with people, everyone is afraid of him, running away from him, even being treated with contempt with his wife. After Carnegie's speech, when this leader began to treat both the spouse and the subordinates sincerely, everyone saw him well, the reputation increased, and his own mood rose.

Another of the secrets of treatment is a crush in a relationship with people. D. Carnegie believes that in Zhang, we stand in the desire to do good to each other. For example, if traffic drivers, employees of Public Service, cooks, hairdressers, sellers are friendly, humble, considerate, use the words "we are pleased to serve you", their reputation will increase, their fans will increase, people will use their services more.

Children are taught from youth to communication first in the family, and then

in educational institutions. One of the ways to teach communication is to formulate in the style of training. The child is taught to communicate in kindergarten, where the educator conducts various classes. At first, such methods as elementary behavior, how to talk to an adult, say hello, express gratitude are transferred to the content

During the school age and later the individual is taught communication by organizing socio - psychological training. The person himself must react positively to these methods, act actively. Because a person can not fully develop both as a subject of activity and as an individual person without communication. Experienced psychologist A.A.Bodalev believes that even in the game activity the child communicates. On the basis of the educational process, the issue of teaching communication is in the first place. While in the process of Labor Education, people constantly need communication. The educational importance of communication is that it helps a person develop his worldview and psyche. That is, all spiritual processes are formed by communication.

By developing the will qualities of an individual, it is also easy to teach him to communicate.

There is also a second side in the formation of the community environment - this is the formation of the spiritual culture of the members of the community. To this end, it is necessary to give the students information that stimulates their feedback on the characteristics of human communication, human personality, evaluation of each other ("I and others", "I through the eyes of others"). It can be organized through essays, conversations, trainings.

Teaching methods of communication through special exercises is similar. It is important to start teaching spiritual culture from the teenage age, because a persistent need for information about one's own personality arises in the same period. In adolescence, conflicting experiences about his "I" begin. At the very first youth - a person who fantasizes about his own state of mind, at an age when communication is very important and extremely selective, information about communication with a person is necessary.

N.P. In the opinion of Anikeeva, in communication with other people, each person plays a certain social role. Roles can reveal the person in full, mask it. But the position-the choice of roles will definitely depend on the essence of a person, his strength, weakness, the level of potential, his ability to self-criticism, punctuality of behavior, his ability to know from an outsider.

Analysis and results. Sometimes failures in communication force young people to hide, spoil the best in themselves, in order to become more self-sufficient, more protective. During early adolescence, Sagittarius and girls experience a state of singles. They do not tell anyone about their feelings. It determines the methods of information and communication about himself and those around him and the desire to organize meaningful communication. For this, it is necessary to have certain knowledge of the spiritual tone. The mental characteristics inherent in each person are determined by the type of nervous system, and are manifested primarily in temperament: at the rate of exposure, both in natural signals (sound, light, color, smell, changes in temperature), and in social signals (speech, event, extreme

sensitivity, emotional reflection, level of anxiety, extraversion, introversion). With extroversion, introversion is brightly manifested in the field of communication as a spiritual description of a person. Extroversion is the view of the individual towards the outside world, introversion is the inner world. People with superior extroversion characteristics associated with a strong type of nervous activity are more sociable, inclined to the circle of contacts, acquaintances. They enthusiastically acquire new acquaintances, like noisy circles. Introverts are people who belong to a weak type of nervous activity. They are inclined to be given to their inner worlds, to their senses. They are very worried about the environment, they prefer a narrow circle of loved ones. Those who were in the middle of the arrow "extroversion-introversion" received the name centroverts in psychology. They are sociable in moderation, prone to loneliness in moderation.

It can also be taught to communicate by working with speech. For example, training, such as reading a poem with a loud voice, telling a story, also contributes to the formation of communication. And children of preschool age are easier to teach communication during play activities.

In teaching communication, it is important to lead by adding game and non-game forms:

1. Introduction of elements of informal communication to the lesson. At the same time, the use of didactic games, the role of the organizer of communication in them is performed by one of the students, and not by the teacher.

2. Focusing attention on the positive aspects of the answer. Students are specially trained to objectively evaluate the answers

of their comrades, at the same time to focus attention on trifles, to learn how to distinguish the most successful aspects of their comrades in their answers. To argue about how to get rid of shortcomings, that is, to influence the deficiency by telling one student himself.

3. Social relations between people have a distinctive feature in the East. This tutorial will help to understand the psychological nature of the changes that are taking place in the spirituality and spirituality of man during the renewal period of society.

Conclusion. The new guides to be created require enriching the spiritual

world of the students and young people, integrating into their minds the foundations of the National idea, educating the sense of patriotism, thinking about the past and the great future, a sense of pride in it, conflicts in the process of formation of new thinking and their elimination.

Thus, looking at the role, essence of communication in the process of formation of the personality of students, we see that it consists of a cognitive and normative process, has a serious impact on the attraction of students to social culture and the formation in it of the social, spiritual direction of the individual, is a means and method of finding a socio –spiritual

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